
Present Status of the Level of Agricultural Mechanization available for Cassava Processing Operations in Ekiti State of Nigeria

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Abstract

Cassava is seen among the common crops grown in Nigeria. This nation can make a lot of foreign exchange from cassava through the export of its finished products. The National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin in April 2018 conducted a National Mechanization survey exercise in Ekiti State purposely to investigate the present level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey exercise in the State. Survey results revealed for the nine (9) cassava processing operations involved showed that cassava peeling and washing operations were 100% dominated by manual processing method in all the cassava processing units visited in the State. A total of 68.96% was recorded for manual processing method for the nine (9) processing operations involved for cassava. It was also noted that a total of 20.31% was recorded for mechanical processing method for the six (6) cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering and milling operations contributed to this figure. Cassava became an important crop almost grown in all parts of Nigeria as the Federal Government of Nigeria showed great interest in promoting the export of cassava chips to China and also the inclusion of 10% of cassava flour with 90% of wheat flour in the making of bread. Because of the importance of this crop to the Nigerian economy, the Ekiti State government is advised to assist cassava processors in their State with loan facility they can use to procure cassava processing machines for use in their various organizations in boosting cassava processing operations in Ekiti State of Nigeria.

Keywords: cassava, processing, method, state, operation, manual

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Introduction

Cassava is one of the most important food items available in Nigeria and the whole of West Africa. It is a popular product because it is cheap and easy to produce in all tropical regions. It is found to be extremely tolerant to environmental stress which makes it suitable for present farming and food system in Africa. Research has shown that cassava is a leading root crop in developing countries (Bunmade, 1990).

Cassava is the most widely cultivated crop in Sub-saharan Africa because of its tolerance to extreme ecological stress conditions and poor soil condition (Okpeke and Onyeagocha, 2015). Cassava is considered as the most productive crop and source of food energy in the tropics. Worldwide, fifteen countries produce in excess of one million tonnes per annum of these, Brazil, Indonesia, Nigeria, Thailand and Zaire are the highest producers and together account for 63 percent of the world's output (Omorjire, 2005).

The main traditional cassava products in Nigeria are *gari*, *fufu*, and *lafun*. According to Phillips *et al.* (2004), cassava is an inexpensive and dependable source of carbohydrates, but the crop lacks nutritional value and is a poor source of protein, vitamins, and minerals (McNulty and Oparinde, 2015). About 70% of processed cassava for human consumption is used for making *gari* in Nigeria among other food products derived from cassava (Oyelade, 2014).

Cassava processing in Nigeria, according to FAO (2004), is described at five levels. Common terms used to describe these capacity levels were household (or cottage), micro, small, medium and large. House-hold level processing typically did not employ any outside labour. The household consumed virtually all the processed products and sold a small amount to raise income for additional household needs. FAO (2004) also reported that most Nigerian processors fell within this category. At micro processing capacity the employment of one or two units of labour might take place while processing a variety of products. This enterprise used batch processing. Nigeria had a few processors in this category. The small and medium processing operations typically employ three to ten workers and were very sparse in Nigeria at present. Large scale processing was virtually non-existent in Nigeria.

There have been improvements made over the years in the design and fabrication of cassava processing machines for the processing of cassava. The availability of different types of machines of varying capacities for cassava processing has increased the efficiency of mechanized cassava processing operations into its various finished

products. The mechanized operation has significantly reduced labor input, processing time, and health risks for processors. It has also increased the quality of cassava products. This study aims at investigating the present level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations in Ekiti State of Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was carried out in Ekiti State which is situated in the southwestern part of Nigeria. The State has a total of 16 Local Government Areas. According to Adetoro and Dada (2017), Ekiti State is mainly an upland zone, rising over 250 meters above sea level. It lies on an area underlain by metamorphic rock. It is generally an undulating part of the country with a characteristic landscape that consists of old plains broken by step-sided out-crops that may occur singularly or in groups or ridges. Such rocks out-crops exist mainly at Aramoko, Efon-Alaiye, Ikere-Ekiti, Igbara-odo-Ekiti and Okemesi-Ekiti. The State is dotted with rugged hills, notable ones being Ikere-Ekiti hills in the south, Efon-Alaiye hills on the western boundary and Ado-Ekiti hills in the centre. The State enjoys tropical climate with two distinct seasons. These are the rainy season (April - October) and the dry season (November - March). Temperature ranges between 21° and 28 °C with high humidity. The south westerly wind and the northeast trade winds blow in the rainy and dry (Harmattan) seasons, respectively. Tropical forest exists in the south, while savannah occupies the northern peripheries.

The land in Ekiti, according to https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ekiti_State, is buoyant in agricultural resources with cocoa as its leading cash crop. It was largely known that Ekiti land constituted well over 40% of the cocoa products of the famous old Western Region. The land is also known for its forest resources, notably timber. Because of the favourable climatic conditions, the land enjoys luxuriant vegetation, thus, it has abundant resources of different species of timber. Food crops such as yam, cassava, and also grains like rice and maize are grown in large quantities. Other notable crops such as kola nut and varieties of fruits are also cultivated in commercial quantities.

2.2 Research Methodology

The study involves the use of primary source of data to obtain relevant information needed for this study. The structured questionnaires used for this study was designed by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin. The structured questionnaire was used to embark on a National Mechanization survey exercise in Ekiti State. The survey was carried out in April 2018 using competent and experienced staff of

the Ekiti State Agricultural Development Programme office that are familiar with the terrain of the State. A total of 401 questionnaires were taken to Ekiti State for the National Mechanization survey exercise by one of the key Technical staff of the Centre (NCAM) for the purpose of organizing a one day induction workshop programme for the enumerators to be used for the survey exercise. These enumerators were trained on how the structured questionnaires would be filled by the respondents. The NCAM survey questionnaires were administered in the 16 Local Government Areas of the State. The stratified sampling technique was used for conducting the survey. During the course of carrying out the survey, NCAM in their own part monitored the survey activity by paying personal visit to some of the target groups in the different Local Government Areas of the State as a way to ensure that information provided by the enumerators were genuine. A total of 287 questionnaires were returned back to NCAM as filled questionnaires. The returned questionnaires were thoroughly scrutinized one after the other by the same Technical staff so as to ensure that the proper information needed from the survey carried out were properly provided for use during data capturing. After data capturing, the captured questionnaires were sorted out by separating those into agro-processing occupation from other occupations contained in the structured questionnaire. A total of 229 agro-processors were found in Ekiti State as 116 of these agro-processors were noticed to fall under those into cassava processing operations. The 116 questionnaires meant for those into cassava processing operations were specifically used for this study.

Statistical Tool

Data obtained from the 116 respondents into cassava processing operations in Ekiti State were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis involving frequency counts and percentage. The SPSS statistical package of version 25.0.0.0 was used for the data computation.

Results and Discussion

The summary of the data computed for the agro-processors into cassava processing operations in Ekiti State is presented in Table 1. It is good to note from Table 1, that a total of 229 agro-processing units were visited in the State out of which 116 agro-processing units representing 50.66% were into cassava processing operations. It can be deduced from Table 1, that there are 9 cassava processing operations captured in the structured questionnaires designed by NCAM for use in the National Mechanization survey exercise carried out in Ekiti State. Arranging the outcome of those that picked manual processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, results

obtained revealed that we have a total of 116 representing 100% of the cassava processing units visited adopt manual processing method for cassava peeling and washing operations, respectively. A total of 110 representing 94.83% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of bagging cassava. A total of 109 representing 93.97% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of drying cassava. A total of 90 representing 77.57% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of chipping cassava. A total of 84 representing 72.42% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of the garification of cassava. A total of 37 representing 31.90% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of milling cassava. A total of 34 representing 29.31% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of dewatering cassava mash. A total of 24 representing 20.69% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the manual processing method of grating cassava. A total of 68.96% was recorded for manual processing method for the 9 processing operations involved for cassava.

Likewise, arranging the outcome of those that picked mechanical processing method from top to lowest in terms of number and percentage involvement, we have a total of 87 representing 75% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for grating cassava.

A total of 70 representing 60.34% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of dewatering cassava mash. A total of 49 representing 42.24% of the cassava processing units visited engage in the mechanical processing method of milling cassava. However, a total of 2 representing 1.72% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for chipping, drying and garification of cassava, respectively. This mechanization level recorded for these three important operations of cassava processing looks very low thereby slowing down the process of producing cassava into its various finished products in the State. A total of 20.31% was recorded for mechanical processing methods for the 6 cassava processing operations involved as grating, dewatering and milling of cassava contributed to this figure.

It can be seen from the analysis carried out as shown in Table 1, that peeling and washing operations of cassava is dominated by manual processing method in the 116 cassava processing units visited in Ekiti State. The adoption of mechanized cassava operations can only be highly seen in the areas of grating (75%), dewatering (60.34%) and milling (42.24%) operations. It should be noted that data captured for those cassava processing

Table 1. Results of Level of Agricultural Mechanization obtained for Cassava Processing operations in Ekiti State

Processing operations	Level of Agricultural Mechanization					
	MN		MC		UD	
	A	B (%)	A	B (%)	A	B (%)
Peeling	116	100	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Washing	116	100	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Grating	24	20.69	87	75.00	5	4.31
Chipping	90	77.57	2	1.72%	24	20.69
Dewatering	34	29.31	70	60.34	12	10.35
Drying	109	93.97	2	1.72	5	4.31
Garification	84	72.42	2	1.72	30	25.86
Milling	37	31.90	49	42.24	30	25.86
Bagging	110	94.83	Nil	Nil	6	5.17
Total	720	N/A	212	N/A	112	N/A
	(68.96%)		(20.31%)		(10.73%)	

Keynote: A = Frequency count; B = Frequency count in its percentage value; MN = Manual operation; MC = Mechanical operation; UD = Undecided; N/A = Not applicable

Note: Total No. into agro-processing activity in Ekiti State = 229; Total No. of agro-processors into cassava processing operation = 116; Percentage of agro-processors into cassava processing = 50.66%.

units visited that picked undecided for their unit operation was not considered for discussion in this study as all discussion were based on those that choose between manual and mechanical means of processing cassava. For record purpose, a total of 10.73% was recorded for those that picked undecided in 7 of their unit operations since peeling and washing operations of cassava in Ekiti State is 100% manually done.

Conclusion

A National Mechanization survey exercise was carried out in April 2018 to determine the present status of the level of agricultural mechanization available for cassava processing operations in Ekiti State of Nigeria. Investigation revealed that all the cassava processing units visited in the State adopt manual processing method for peeling and washing of cassava. It was also noted that 75%, 60.34% and 42.24% of the cassava processing units visited adopt mechanical processing method for grating, dewatering and milling of cassava, respectively. However, operations such as chipping, drying and gratification of cassava all had 1.72% involvement each in the area of utilizing mechanical processing method thereby making these three cassava processing operations to be nearly dominated by manual processing method. Cassava processing is seen as a lucrative business in Nigeria and in order to make Ekiti State food sufficiency in the production of cassava products, the State government is hereby advised to assist cassava processors in the State with loan facility they can use to procure cassava processing machines needed for boosting cassava processing operations in the State.

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